

The Fast Lane of Shopping: Quick Commerce's Grip on Modern Consumers

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Abstract – Digital technology has radically changed the retail business and given rise to quick commerce. Quick commerce offers products that are delivered within minutes and has greatly changed consumer shopping habits and expectations. The current study, “The Fast Lane of Shopping: Quick Commerce's Grip on Modern Consumers,” focuses on how quick commerce platforms influence purchase habits, spending, and decision-making. Data for the study were collected through a structured questionnaire distributed to the respondents using simple random sampling. Analysis of the data was done using descriptive and Chi-Square tests. Results from this study indicate that convenience, urgency, and fast delivery are the leading factors behind the adoption of quick commerce. Although quick commerce is rapidly gaining popularity among modern consumers, traditional stores remain important in planning and bulk purchases.

Keywords – Quick Commerce, Consumer Behaviour, Online Retail, Digital Platforms, Instant Delivery.

I. INTRODUCTION

The retail industry has also witnessed dramatic changes with the advent of digital technologies and smartphones, as well as online payment systems. One of the recent changes in retailing has been the emergence of quick commerce, the next phase of e-commerce. This new way to get things quickly, often in 10 to 30 minutes, will appeal to shoppers who are becoming increasingly dependent on convenience and speed.

Quick commerce systems operate through hyperlocal fulfilment centres (dark stores) that store often-ordered items in the vicinity. Orders placed through mobile applications are processed quickly and are delivered via last mile delivery services. These companies can thereby deliver groceries, household goods, and other items as needed on an urgent basis.

In the last few years, there has been a shift in consumer behaviour from planned shopping to more spontaneous, convenience-driven shopping. They are now using quick commerce platforms for urgent needs and last-minute purchases. The rapid expansion of quick commerce also brings concerns regarding impulse buying, sustainability, and longevity of traditional stores. The objective of this study is to examine the impact of quick commerce on modern consumers and how these platforms influence their purchasing behavior and shopping preferences.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the impact of income level, price sensitivity, and transaction costs on consumers' adoption of Quick Commerce.
2. To analyse consumer-level readiness, infrastructure-related expectations and behaviours towards expanding Quick Commerce in Tier 3 and Tier 4 cities of India.

3. To assess the impact of urgency and convenience on the use of quick commerce platforms.
4. To determine how fast commerce has affected modern consumers' shopping habits in comparison with traditional commerce.

II. METHODS AND TECHNIQUES

The study utilized both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected from respondents via a questionnaire designed to collect information on their shopping habits, spending behaviour, and perceptions of quick commerce sites. Secondary data were collected from journal articles, online publications, and industry reports relating to quick commerce and consumer behaviour. Focusing on those consumers who regularly use quick commerce sites for buying groceries, household goods, and personal care products, this study examines the impact of quick commerce on consumer choices, shopping patterns, and purchasing patterns in the digital retail environment. There were 200 respondents selected for analysis. The study was conducted using Simple Random Sampling, where every member of the population was equally likely to be selected. This eliminates bias and ensures fair selection of each respondent.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Out of 200 people surveyed, 29 % of the respondents are from the age group of 26 – 35 years, 25 % of the respondents are from the age group 18 – 25 years, 24.5 % of the respondents are from the age group below 18 years and 21.5 % of the respondents are from the age group 36 – 45 years. 31 % of the respondents prefer Quick Commerce for regular grocery shopping, 26 % of the respondents prefer local Kirana stores, 22.5 % of the respondents prefer a combination of all modes and 20.5 % of the respondents prefer supermarkets.

IV. CHI SQUARE ANALYSIS

Hypothesis 1 Variables used:

- Age of respondents
- Preferred Mode of Grocery Shopping

Null Hypothesis (H₀):

There is no significant relationship between age and preferred mode of grocery shopping.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):

There is a significant relationship between age and preferred mode of grocery shopping.

Table: Age Group and Preferred Mode of Grocery Shopping

Age Group	Quick Commerce	Traditional Store	Total
18-25	45	15	60
26-35	35	15	50
36-45	20	20	40
More than 45	10	40	50
Total	110	90	200

	Value	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided) (p)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.15	9	0.82
N of Valid Cases	200		

Since $p > 0.05$, Null hypothesis (H₀) cannot be rejected.

Interpretation

The Chi-square test was applied to analyse whether respondents' age is associated with the preferred mode of grocery shopping.

The obtained χ^2 value of 5.15 with 9 degrees of freedom results in a p-value of 0.82, which is significantly higher than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

There is no significant relationship between age and preferred mode of grocery shopping.

Hypothesis 2 Variables used:

- Gender of respondents
- Frequency of Quick Commerce usage Null Hypothesis (H₀):

There is no significant relationship between gender and frequency of quick commerce usage. Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):

There is a significant relationship between gender and frequency of quick commerce usage.

Table: Gender and Frequency of Quick Commerce Usage

Gender	Daily	2-3 times a week	Once a week	Rarely	Total
Female	20	18	30	40	108
Male	18	20	23	31	92
Total	38	38	53	71	200

Gender and Frequency of Quick Commerce Usage

	Value	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided) (p)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.14	4	0.71
N of Valid Cases	200		

Since $p > 0.05$, Null hypothesis (H₀) cannot be rejected.

Interpretation

The Chi-square test was applied to analyze whether respondents' gender is associated with the frequency of quick commerce usage.

The obtained χ^2 value of 2.14 with 4 degrees of freedom results in a p-value of 0.71, which is significantly higher than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

There is no significant relationship between gender and frequency of quick commerce usage.

Hypothesis 3 Variables used:

- Monthly household income

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- Average spending per order in quick commerce Null Hypothesis (H₀):

There is no significant association between the monthly household income and the average spending per order on quick commerce platforms.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):

There is a significant association between the monthly household income and the average spending per order on quick commerce platforms.

Table: Monthly Household Income and Average Spending per Order

Monthly Income	Below ₹300	₹300–₹700	₹700–₹1500	Above ₹1500	Total
Below ₹20,000	25	20	18	18	81
₹20,001 – ₹40,000	10	12	8	8	38
₹40,001 – ₹70,000	9	10	18	20	57
₹70,001 – ₹1,00,000	8	8	4	4	24
Total	52	50	48	50	200

Monthly Household Income and Average Spending per Order

	Value	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided) (p)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.14	4	0.71
N of Valid Cases	200		

Since $p > 0.05$, Null hypothesis (H₀) cannot be rejected.

Interpretation

The Chi-square test was applied to analyze whether monthly household income is associated with the average spending per order.

The obtained χ^2 value of 7.35 with 9 degrees of freedom results in a p-value of 0.6, which is significantly higher than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

There is no significant relationship between monthly household income and average spending per order.

Findings of the Study

The major findings of the study were:

- Comfort and speed of delivery are the primary factors influencing rapid online shopping.
- Many consumers rely on quick commerce for urgent purchases and forgotten items.
- Quick commerce platforms are widely used among young consumers aged 18–25.
- UPI is the most commonly used payment method among respondents.
- Consumers still prefer traditional stores for purchasing fresh fruits and vegetables.
- Quick commerce and traditional retail are likely to coexist rather than replace one another.

V. CONCLUSION

The study shows that quick commerce is increasingly shaping modern consumer habits, as it ensures fast delivery, convenience, and easy access to everyday necessities. It is more beneficial for urgent needs and small, frequent purchases than bulk purchases. Yet, traditional stores are still relevant, especially for planned and larger shopping transactions. In order to thrive, retailers need to improve logistics, reduce operating costs, and maintain customer trust.

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